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Review Paper

A Review of Phytochemical, Psychopharmacological Activity of *Cleome viscosa* Linn

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ABSTRACT

Cleome viscosa Linn. (Capparaceae), also known as "Hurhur," is an annual, sticky herb that is commonly found as a weed in the plains of India, Africa, Pakistan, and other places. The plant and its parts (leaves, seeds, roots, etc.) are used traditionally to cure a variety of diseases. The review reveals the collection of important pharmacological activities like antimicrobial, analgesic, antiemetic, antidiarrheal, hepatoprotective, antifibrotic, antitumor, anticonvulsant, and psychopharmacological. In order to help researchers find new chemical entities, the review highlights the traditional, phytochemical, and pharmacological knowledge available on *Cleome viscosa* Linn

INTRODUCTION

Plants have been utilized as raw materials for medications since ancient times. The general public in India has extensive knowledge of the therapeutic value of plants. In India, some 3,500 plant species can be used to make crude drugs. There are over 2,500 plants that are significant for medicine. Although certain plant species are regarded as weeds, they also have vital medical uses. Plant-based products are employed in a variety of conventional and contemporary therapeutic approaches. The use of herbal medicine is becoming more and more popular in

the modern era. The development of contemporary biotechnology and bioinformatics methods leads to the discovery of new medications. [1] Herbal medicines are used increasingly frequently in the modern period as people's faith in natural remedies grows daily. Natural compounds extracted from bacteria and higher plants are used to find new, clinically effective medications. [2] Every year, the sticky herb *Cleome viscosa* Linn., often known as wild or dog mustard, belongs to the Capparaceae family and is a common weed in the plains of Pakistan, India, China, Ceylon, Africa, and other tropical regions of the world. The plant's leaves, seeds, and roots are used extensively in traditional

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medicine as an anthelmintic, antiscorbutic, antiseptic, heart stimulant, carminative, febrifuge and sudorific, anticonvulsant, antidiarrheal, and to treat skin conditions. [3] In India, it is referred to as "Hurhur." The plant *Cleome viscosa* Linn. has historically been used as an antimalarial medication and for uterine and blood disorders. In curries, the strong seeds and seed pods are used in place of mustard. [4]

BIOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION AND TAXONOMY

The annual *Cleome viscosa* Linn. grows upright to a height of 30 to 90 cm. The plant's stem has grooves and is heavily covered in simple and glandular hairs. The plant has three to five foliolate leaves. Petioles on lower leaves are 2.5–5 cm long and progressively get shorter as they ascend. They are sessile bracts. Leaflets can be acute or obtuse, elliptical, oblong, or obovate. Petioles are hairy and short. The yellow flowers are axillary and develop into a loose raceme. Pedicels are hairy, terete, and thin. Sepals have an oblong, lanceolate, glandular, pubescent exterior and are 4.5 cm in length. Petals are veined, oblong-obovate, and about 12 mm long. There are more than 20 stamens. Capsules are 5-6.3 by 0.4 cm, hairy, obliquely striated, compressed, tapering at both ends, and end with a 3 mm-long style. When ripe, seeds are sub globose, slightly transversely striated, and brown to black in colour. (Figure 1). [5]

CLASSIFICATION

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Subkingdom: Tracheobionta
- Superdivision: Spermatophyta
- Division: Magnoliophyta
- Class: Magnoliopsida
- Subclass: Dilleniidae
- Order: Capparales
- Family: Capparaceae

- Genus: *Cleome* Linn
- Species: *Cleome viscosa* Linn

Figure 1: *Cleome viscosa* Linn Plant³

Figure 2: *Cleome viscosa* Linn Plant

DISTRIBUTION

Cleome viscosa Linn. is found all over the world's tropical climates. India, the United States, Nigeria, China, Ceylon, Pakistan, and Africa are among the places where it happens.

PYTOCHEMISTRY

Phytochemical studies have been done on the root, stem, leaf, and seed of the plant in order to identify and describe chemicals. Terpenes, flavonoids, phenol carboxylic acid, and polyphenols were found in the extracts after a preliminary phytochemical screening. [2] Extracts from leaves, seeds, and roots have been found to include monoterpenes, hydrocarbons, sesquiterpenoids, and oxygenated derivatives. Heptane-4-one, α -pinene, camphene, dehydrosabene, 6-Methylhept-5-ene-2-one, β -pinene, myrcene, p-cymene, limonene, E-ocimene, α -terpenol, alloocimene, citronellic acid, coumarin, cedrene, α -amorphene, and ethyl palmitate were among the compounds found in the leaf extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. The root extract included Oct-1-ene, α -pinene, β -pinene, myrcene, p-cymene, E-ocimene, dehydrolinalool, undecane, allo-ocimene, limonene oxide, α -terpenol, Decan-2-ol, citronellic acid, and Deca-

2,4-dien-1-al. Oct-1-ene, Heptane-4-one, Heptane-2-one, Non-1-ene, α -pinene, dehydrosabenene, 6-Methylhept-5-ene-2-one, Eocimene, myrcene, p-cymene, limonene, dehydrolinalool, undecan, limonene oxide, α -tepeniol, benzoic acid, Deca-2,4-dien-1-al, Decan-2-ol, Gerniol, Undec-10-e-1-al, and coumarin were found in the seed extract. Seeds were found to contain six viscocic

compounds, including viscosin (monomethoxy trihydroxyflavone).⁷ A novel glycoside called eriodictyol 5-rhamnoside has been extracted from the whole plant.⁸ In seed extracts, cleomiscosin A and B were found.⁹ Glu-cocapparin, glucoceleomin (glucosinolates), and cleomaldeic acid (3E, 7E, 11E) 20-oxocembra-3, 7, 11, 15-tetraen-19-oic acid), a macrocyclic diterpene, have been extracted from the whole plant.¹¹ Table 1 lists a few of the phytoconstituents.

Figure 3: Important phytoconstituents of cleome viscosa Linn

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTION

Researchers have concentrated on its pharmacological screening because to its traditional claim in literature. Among all the actions described, this text explains a few key ones as.

ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY

Several extracts of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. seeds were used for the antibacterial investigation. There were eight different types of microbes employed. These eight microbial species were evaluated against petroleum ether extract, chloroform extract, ethyl acetate extract, ethanol extract, and aqueous extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. seeds. Additionally, clinical pus samples from individuals with earaches were used. Significant

antibacterial activity has been demonstrated by the test materials. It was shown that the zones of inhibition ranged from 10 to 17 mm. additionally, the extracts' minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values against microorganisms were calculated; these values vary from 0.1 to 0.45.¹²

ANALGESIC ACTIVITY

The analgesic activity of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. in experimental animal models was investigated. *Cleome viscosa* Linn dosages of 75 mg/kg body weight, 100 mg/kg body weight, and 125 mg/kg body weight reduced the amount of writhes. seeds fixed oil in contrast to the control and aspirin treatment. At doses of 75 mg/kg body weight, 100 mg/kg body weight, and 125 mg/kg body weight, fixed oil reduces the number of writhes by 91.69%,

92.33%, and 96.0%, respectively. The aspirin-treated mice group writhed 11 times at a dose of 150 mg/kg body weight. However, there were 62 writhes in the control group; therefore, aspirin had a favorable effect by reducing writhes by 82.42%. One useful technique for assessing peripherally active analgesics is the acetic acid-induced writhing method. [3]

ANTIEMETIC ACTIVITY

The antiemetic effects of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. fixed oil on young chicks were assessed. The retches number is decreased by 84.43%, 85.56%, and 91.77%, respectively, when fixed oil is administered at doses of 75 mg/kg body weight, 100 mg/kg body weight, and 125 mg/kg body weight. The group of chicks treated with chlorpromazine experienced 47 retches at a dose of 150 mg/kg body weight. However, chlorpromazine decreased the retches by 30.56% compared to the control group, which had 68 retches. *Cleome viscosa*. Compared to chlorpromazine, seed oil significantly reduced emesis. These findings lead to the conclusion that the fixed oil of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. Possesses antiemetic properties and is similar to the nausea-relieving medication chlorpromazine. [3]

ANTIDIARRHOEAL ACTIVITY

"A study was conducted" to assess the anti-diarrheal activity of a methanolic extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. (Family: Capparidaceae) against different rat models of diarrhoea. The extract showed inhibitory action in rats with PGE2-induced enteropooling and castor oil-induced diarrhoea. The extract also significantly decreased the rats' gastrointestinal motility in the charcoal meal test. The outcomes demonstrated that *Cleome viscosa* Linn is a potent anti-diarrheal medication. [13]

HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

Cleome viscosa Linn's hepatoprotective properties in experimental animal models. The effectiveness of ethanolic extract against hepatotoxicity caused by carbon tetrachloride was assessed.

The test substance was proven to be effective in "in vivo" and histological investigations. In animals poisoned with carbon tetrachloride, the extract successfully shortened the "thiopental"-induced sleep. The ethanolic extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. exhibited comparable effects to "Silymarin," a common hepatoprotective medication. It was evident from the results that the ethanolic extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. is a potent hepatoprotective agent. [14]

ANTIFIBROTIC ACTIVITY

The study was performed to evaluate the antifibrotic activity of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. ethanolic extract. Rats were given carbon tetrachloride to cause liver fibrosis. The degree of liver fibrosis was determined by measuring the levels of serum enzymes, thiobarbituric acid, and liver hydroxyproline. Following the administration of carbon tetrachloride, blood enzyme levels, thiobarbituric acid, hydroxyproline, and total platelets were all raised. Following treatment with two distinct dosages of ethanolic extract from *Cleome viscosa* Linn., the levels of hydroxyproline, thiobarbituric acid, and serum enzymes decreased. *Cleome viscosa* Linn. ethanolic extract decreased liver weight, which had grown following the administration of carbon tetrachloride, which results in collagen deposition. It was evident from the outcome that *Cleome viscosa* Linn. An efficient antifibrotic medication is ethanolic extract. [15]

ANTITUMOR ACTIVITY

A study was conducted to assess *Cleome viscosa* Linn's anticancer potential. in animal models used in experiments. Following a 24-hour tumour inoculation, the extract was given daily for 14 days

at doses of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg body weight. After the last injection and an 18-hour fast, the mice were killed. *Cleome viscosa* Linn's impact. The methanolic extract of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. Was found to significantly reduce the tumour volume, packed cell volume, and viable cell count. Additionally, it prolongs the life span of mice with Ehrlich ascites carcinoma tumours. It also makes mice with Ehrlich ascites carcinoma tumours live longer. It was evident from the results that *Cleome viscosa* Linn. In Ehrlich ascites carcinoma bearing mice, methanolic extract has a strong anticancer effect. [16]

ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY

A study was conducted to assess *Cleome viscosa* Linn's anticonvulsant activity. seeds extract using the Pentylenetetrazole Induced Seizures (PTZ) and Maximum Electroshock Induced Seizures (MES) tests. Both ethanolic and aqueous seed extract demonstrated notable efficacy in convulsions caused by MES and PTZ. [17]

PSYCHOPHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY

Cleome viscosa Linn for several psychopharmacological actions, including general behaviour, exploratory behaviour, muscle relaxant activity, phenobarbitone-induced sleeping time, and effects on normal body temperature in rats and mice. The methanolic extract was assessed. Following extract administration, there was a decrease in spontaneous activity, a decrease in the exploratory behavioural pattern by the head dip and Y-maze test, a decrease in the muscle relaxant by the rota rod, a 30-degree inclined screen and traction tests, and a drop in body temperature. Additionally, extract significantly increases the amount of time that phenobarbitone induces sleep. *Cleome viscosa* Linn. Methanolic extract had a notable psychopharmacological impact at doses of 200–400 mg/kg. [18, 19]

CLEOME VISCOSA LINN-BIODIESEL APPLICATION

Biodiesel, often known as "vegetable-oil or animal fat based fuel," is made of alkyl (methyl, propyl, or ethyl) esters through a chemical reaction between lipids (vegetable oil, animal fat) and alcohol. An alternative fuel to diesel that burns cleanly is biodiesel. It is made from renewable resources that are grown domestically. Alkyl esters are found in a range of biodiesels, although they are absent from petroleum-derived diesel's alkanes and aromatic hydrocarbons. Biodiesel was made from the oil of *Cleome viscosa* Linn. seeds. The blended component of biodiesel's physiochemical characteristics were examined. Specific gravity, density, viscosity, flash point, fire point, cloud point, pour point, smoke point, pH, viscosity, carbon residue, saponification value, acid value, and iodine value are among the physico-chemical characteristics evaluated. [20]

TOXICITY STUDIES

According to reports, *Cleome viscosa* Linn. Is harmless when tested for acute toxicity in female Swiss albino mice. [17]

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